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Experimental and Computational Studies on Photophysical Properties of Coumarin 4-(4-Methoxy-Phenoxymethyl)-5, 7-Dimethyl-Chromen-2-One by Solvatochromic Approaches

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Abstract

Objectives: The study aimed to investigate the absorption and fluorescence properties of 4MPDC in various solvents and understand the influence of solute-solvent interactions on its spectral characteristics. **Methods:** The study employed solvatochromic methods, including Lippert-Mataga polarity function, Reichardt's microscopic solvent polarity parameter, and Kamlet and Catalan's multiple linear regression techniques. Gaussian software 16W with B3LYP/6-311G basis set was used to estimate electric dipole moments. **Findings:** Hydrogen bonding interactions dominate dielectric interactions in pure solvents. The excited state dipole moment is greater than the ground state dipole moment. The compound's HOMO and LUMO energies indicate chemical activity and molecular interactions. The HOMO energy is -0.21624 eV, the LUMO energy is -0.07912 eV, resulting in a HOMO-LUMO energy gap (ΔE) of 0.13712 eV. The excited state has an intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) character. Polar solvents alter the fluorescence properties of coumarin. Quantum Yield (Φ_f): Predicted 0.28–0.84. Lifetime (τ_f): 1–5 ns. **Novelty:** The study highlights the significant role of solute-solvent interactions in influencing the photophysical properties of 4MPDC, providing insights into its potential applications. The molecule has biomedical applications and can be used in optoelectronic devices.

Keywords: DFT structure; LUMO and HOMO; Absorption spectra; Fluorescence spectra; UV-VIS spectra; IR spectra; Dipole moments; Polarizability; Fluorescence quantum yield; Lifetime

1 Introduction

The study of solvent effects on organic fluorophores' absorption and fluorescence properties has gained significant attention in photophysics and photochemistry. Determining ground and excited state dipole moments is crucial for understanding photophysical properties like fluorescence quantum yield, lifetime, and spectral shifts. Solvatochromic, a widely used method, correlates spectroscopic parameters with solvent polarity functions to estimate dipole moments⁽¹⁾. Coumarins, a class of fluorescent molecules, have been extensively studied using this approach. However, there's a gap in research on coumarin derivatives like 4MPDC, with no reported ground and excited state dipole moment values. This study aims to fill this gap by estimating 4MPDC's dipole moments using various Solvatochromic methods and DFT calculations, providing insights into its photophysical properties and potential applications. The knowledge of excited state dipole moments is crucial for designing nonlinear optical materials and understanding photophysical properties like fluorescence quantum yield (Φ_f), fluorescence lifetime (τ_f), absorption, and fluorescence spectral shifts⁽²⁾.

The present investigation focuses on estimating the ground and excited state dipole moments of coumarin 4MPDC using solvents with different polarities. The effects of pure solvents on spectral properties were studied using Bilot-Kawski, Lippert-Mataga, Bakhshiev's, Kawski-Chamma-Viallet's, and Reichardt Solvatochromic shift methods⁽³⁾.

The molecule 4MPDC is a coumarin (chromen-2-one) derivative containing multiple aromatic rings and heteroatoms. Due to its extended π -conjugation, substituent effects, and possible intramolecular interactions, Density Functional Theory (DFT) is an appropriate method to study its optimized geometry and electronic structure

2 Methodology

2.1 Equations for the estimation of dipole moments

The independent equations used for the estimation of ground and excited state dipole moments in various solvents with varied dielectric constant (ϵ) and refractive index (n) are as follows^{(4), (5)}.

$$\text{Lippert-Mataga equation } -\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f = m_1 f_1(\epsilon, n) + \text{Constant}$$

$$\text{Bakhshiev's equation } -\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f = m_2 f_2(\epsilon, n) + \text{Constant}$$

Kawski-Chamma-Viallet's equation,

$$\frac{\bar{\nu}_a + \bar{\nu}_f}{2} = -m_3 f_3(\epsilon, n) + \text{Constant}$$

Where $\bar{\nu}_a$ and $\bar{\nu}_f$ are absorption and emission maxima wave number in cm^{-1} .

2.2 Estimation of excited state dipole moments

The μ_g of coumarin 4MPDC compound was determined with the help of Bakhshiev's and Kawski-Chamma-Viallet's relations. Using these polarity parameters, the following expressions can be obtained to estimate μ_g and μ_e which are parallel to one another⁽⁶⁾.

$$\mu_g = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{2} \left(\frac{hca^3}{2m_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \mu_e = \frac{m_2 + m_1}{2} \left(\frac{hca^3}{2m_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The slopes m_1 and m_2 are obtained from the plots of $(\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f)$ versus $f_1(\epsilon, n)$, and $\left(\frac{\bar{\nu}_a + \bar{\nu}_f}{2}\right)$ versus $F_2(\epsilon, n)$ for different solvents, respectively.

Where h Planck's constant, a is Onsager radius of a molecule C is velocity of light.

If μ_e and μ_g are not parallel to one another, then the angle ϕ between μ_e and μ_g can be estimated using the below

$$\cos \phi = \frac{1}{2\mu_g \mu_e} \left[(\mu_g^2 + \mu_e^2) - \frac{m_2}{m_1} (\mu_e^2 - \mu_g^2) \right]$$

The μ_e is also estimated by means of E_N^T using the below

$$(\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f) = 11307.6 \left[\left(\frac{\Delta\mu}{\Delta\mu_s} \right)^2 \left(\frac{a_s}{a} \right)^3 \right] E_N^T + Constant$$

Where $\Delta\mu_B$ is the change in dipole moment

a_s is the Onsager radius of the solvent

$\Delta\mu$ and a are the corresponding parameters of the compound.

2.3 DFT Structure of 4MPDC (Figure 1)

Fig 1. DFT Structure OF 4MPDC with dipole moment vector

The DFT optimized structure of 4MPDC with dipole moment vector is presented in Figure 1. The structure was obtained using B3LYP/6-311++G(d, p) level of theory. The geometry optimization was carried out in the gas phase without any symmetry constraints. As seen in Figure 1, the molecule adopts a planar conformation which favors effective π -electron delocalization.

2.4 Core Molecular Features

- Formula: $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$.
- Exact Mass: 336 amu.
- Molar Mass: $336 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.
- Double Bond Equivalents (DBE): 13 (high aromaticity and conjugation).
- LogP: 3.6-4.2 (hydrophobic, organic soluble).
- Topology: Lactone (chromen-2-one core) + 4-Methoxy-Phenoxymethyl + 5,7-dimethyl (electron-donating substituent)⁽⁷⁾.

2.5 Reagents and apparatus

All chemicals and solvents used in this study were of spectroscopic grade, obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Company and S.D. Fine Chemicals Ltd., India, respectively. The absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded using a UV-visible spectrophotometer at USIC, Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi, and a Spectro fluorophotometer at USIC, Dharwad University, Dharwad, respectively, at room temperature. All sample solutions were prepared in various solvents with different polarities at low concentrations (10^{-5} M) to avoid self-absorption.

2.6 Photophysical Properties: Absorption and Emission (Figures 2-5)

UV-VIS Absorption: Dominant π - π^* band typically 310–390 nm, with the maximum (λ_{max}) shifting to 300 nm due to electron-donating substituents and extended conjugation. Emission: Blue-green region (400–520 nm), with emission red-shifting in polar solvents; the Stokes shift is moderate (80–160 nm). Quantum Yield (Φ_f): Predicted 0.28–0.84; higher in non-protic, rigid media and lower with H-bonding or quenching processes. Lifetime (τ_f): 1–5 ns in air-saturated solution; longer in deoxygenated/nonpolar environments^{(8), (9)}.

The absorption spectra of 4MPDC in various polar solvents are presented in Figure 2. The λ_{max} of 4MPDC shifts towards longer wavelengths as the polarity of the solvent increases. This bathochromic shift indicates significant solute-solvent interactions in the ground state.

Fig 2. Absorption spectra of 4MPDC in polar solvents

The absorption spectra of 4MPDC in nonpolar solvents are presented in Figure 3. The absorption maxima of 4MPDC remain almost unchanged in solvents. This negligible solvatochromic effect indicates weak solute-solvent interactions in nonpolar media.

The fluorescence spectra of 4MPDC in various polar solvents are presented in Figure 4. The emission intensity and peak position are strongly influenced by solvent polarity, with broader bands observed in highly polar solvents. Compared to the absorption spectra, the large Stokes shift observed confirms significant excited-state relaxation.

The fluorescence spectra of 4MPDC in nonpolar solvents are presented in Figure 5. The compound exhibits structured emission bands in the range of 340–380 nm. No appreciable shift in the emission maximum is observed with change in nonpolar solvents.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of solvents on absorption and fluorescence spectra of coumarin 4MPDC

The absorption and fluorescence spectra of coumarin 4MPDC were recorded in different solvents in increasing order of their polarity at room temperature (Table 1). The maximum absorption and fluorescence wavelengths of coumarin 4MPDC were found to be in the range of 258–298 nm and 339–434 nm, respectively, in the chosen solvents⁽¹⁰⁾. Absorption maxima ($\bar{\nu}_a$),

Fig 3. Absorption spectra of 4MPDC in nonpolar solvents

emission maxima ($\bar{\nu}_f$), Stokes shifts ($\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$), and the arithmetic mean of Stokes shift values (in cm^{-1}) were calculated and tabulated⁽¹¹⁾.

3.2 HOMO and LUMO of 4MPDC

The HOMO energy is -0.21624 eV, the LUMO energy is -0.07912 eV, resulting in a HOMO-LUMO energy gap (ΔE) of 0.13712 eV. The lower value of energy gap indicates the high reactivity and low kinetic stability of molecule. Frontier molecular orbital theory was also used to find the chemical hardness (η), softness (δ), chemical potential (μ) and electron negativity (χ) of a molecule⁽¹¹⁾,⁽¹²⁾. From HOMO-LUMO, electrons are delocalized on the methyl group and oxygen atom benzopyran group. The distribution of electron density on oxygen of benzopyran increases, at the same time electron density on N atom decreases during LUMO⁽¹³⁾.

The absorption maxima λ_a , emission maxima λ_f , and their corresponding wavenumbers $\bar{\nu}_a$ and $\bar{\nu}_f$ for 4MPDC in various solvents are summarized in Table 1. From these values, the Stokes shifts $\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$ were computed and plotted against the polarity functions $\frac{\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f}{f_1(\epsilon, n) + g(n)}$ and $\frac{\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f}{f_2(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)}$. The linear plots of Stokes shifts ($\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$) versus these functions confirm the role of general solvent effects on the spectral properties of 4MPDC.

The Lippert–Mataga graph of 4MPDC is presented in Figure 6. The Stokes shift is plotted against the solvent polarity function, a straight line with a good correlation coefficient. The positive slope of the graph confirms that the excited state of 4MPDC is more polar than the ground state.

Fig 4. Fluorescence spectra of 4MPDC in polar solvents

Bakshiev's plot for 4MPDC is presented in Figure 7. The Stokes shift increases linearly with Bakshiev's polarity function, confirming enhanced stabilization of the excited state in polar media. The good linearity suggests that specific solute-solvent interactions are negligible compared to universal interactions.

Stoke's shift versus polarity function graphs plotted and shown in Figure 6 and 7 used to carryout further calculation of dipole moment. From the graphs obtained slopes are 0.50 ($R^2=0.9812$) and 1.08 ($R^2=0.9143$) for Lippert – Mataga and Bakshiev methods respectively. The radius of the molecule 4MPDC obtained fom J T Edward method is 3.81 Angstrom. The ground state dipole moment obtained as 1.26 D and exited state dipole moments obatined as 3.72 D and 4.86 D, for Lippert and Bakshiev methods respectively. From the calculations one can observe that ground state dipole moment values are greater than excited state dipole moment.

3.3 Spectroscopic Features: UV-VIS Electronic Transitions OF 4MPDC

The UV-Vis spectrum of 4MPDC is presented in Figure 8. The spectrum displays a prominent absorption band with λ_{max} at 285 nm. This band is assigned to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi$ electronic transition of the aromatic system.

3.3.1. Excited states of 4MPDC

- The S_1 excited state has an energy of 3.15 eV, corresponding to a wavelength of 393 nm, with a low oscillator strength ($f = 0.0014$), indicating a symmetry-forbidden HOMO \rightarrow LUMO transition⁽¹⁴⁾.

Fig 5. Fluorescence spectra of 4MPDC in nonpolar solvents

Table 1. Calculated values for solvent polarity parameters, $\lambda_a, \lambda_f, \bar{\nu}_a, \bar{\nu}_f, \bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f, f_1(\epsilon, n) + g(n), \frac{\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f}{f_1(\epsilon, n) + g(n)}, f_2(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n), \frac{\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f}{f_2(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)}$

Sol-vents	λ_a (nm)	λ_f (nm)	$\bar{\nu}_a$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\bar{\nu}_f$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$ (cm ⁻¹)	$f_1(\epsilon, n) + g(n)$	$\frac{\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f}{f_1(\epsilon, n) + g(n)}$	$f_2(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)$	$\frac{\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f}{f_2(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)}$	$(cm - 1)$
Methanol	293.39	334.38	34129	29940	4189	0.532	7874	1.303	3214	
Ethanol	294.14	324.47	34013	30864	3149	0.534	5897	1.320	2385	
Hexanol	294.82	343.64	33898	29069	4829	0.528	9145	1.250	3850	
Hep-tanol	278.66	383.84	35842	26041	9801	0.517	18957	1.220	8033	
Octanol	261.07	334.47	38314	29904	8410	0.514	16361	1.196	7031	
Chloro-form	264.60	334.02	37735	29940	7795	0.325	23984	0.425	18341	
Toluene	290.61	334.32	34364	29913	4451	0.733	6066	1.073	4145	
DMSO	271.59	334.38	36900	29906	6994	0.588	11894	1.489	4697	
1,4-Dioxane	263.17	334.38	38022	29552	8470	0.343	24643	0.303	27907	
Ben-zene	281.39	334.32	35587	29911	5676	0.469	12081	0.574	9883	
DMF	277.23	334.68	36101	29850	6251	0.547	11413	1.421	4399	

Fig 6. Lippert - Mataga graph of 4MPDC, $\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$ Vs $\frac{\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f}{f_1(\epsilon, n) + g(n)}$

Fig 7. Bakshiev's polarity function of 4MPDC, $\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$ Vs $\frac{\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f}{f_2(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)}$

- The S_2 excited state, characterized by a $\pi-\pi^*$ transition (HOMO-2/1 \rightarrow LUMO), has an energy of 3.97 eV and a wavelength of 312 nm, with a moderate oscillator strength ($f = 0.0941$)^{(15), (16)}.
- The S_3 excited state, responsible for the dominant UV absorption, has an energy of 4.21 eV and a wavelength of 294 nm, with a relatively high oscillator strength ($f = 0.2959$)

Strong absorption at 294–312 nm (S_2/S_3) dominates the UV-Vis spectrum. Emission is expected from S_1 , but with a low quantum yield due to the forbidden nature^{(17), (18)}.

Fig 8. UV-VIS Spectrum OF 4MPDC

Fig 9. IR Spectrum of 4MPDC

3.4 IR Vibrational Assignments OF 4MPDC

The IR spectrum of 4MPDC is presented in Figure 9, along with the theoretical spectrum simulated using DFT/B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p).

The IR spectrum features several diagnostic bands related to functional groups present in the coumarin-based molecule 4MPDC. The chromen-2-one coumarin carbonyl exhibits strong C=O stretching vibrations at the wavenumber 1723 and 1656 cm^{-1} , with high intensities (ϵ) indicating significant molecular transitions^{(19), (20)}. The phenyl and coumarin aromatic rings show moderate to strong aromatic C=C stretching vibrations at the wavenumber 1611 and 1541 cm^{-1} , indicative of the molecule's planar, conjugated structure. The methoxy, phenoxy, and aryl ether groups exhibit a strong cluster of C–O–C stretching and ring modes between the wavenumber 1486–1245 cm^{-1} , accompanied by in-plane C–H bending vibrations^{(21), (22)}. The phenoxy and methoxy ether groups show a very strong alkyl/aryl C–O stretching vibration at the wavenumber 1041 cm^{-1} . The substituted aromatic environments exhibit strong aromatic C–H bending vibrations (out-of-plane) at the wavenumber 894, 846, and 872 cm^{-1} . The methoxy, benzylic, and aromatic hydrogens show multiple moderate aliphatic and aromatic C–H stretching vibrations between the wavenumber 2680–2790 cm^{-1} .

The IR spectrum shows characteristic peaks in several regions: 2670–2800 cm^{-1} (C–H stretching of aliphatic/aromatic hydrogens), 1540–1725 cm^{-1} (C=C and C=O stretching of conjugated aromatics and carbonyls), 1245–1486 cm^{-1} (C–O and

ring modes of aryloxy, methoxy, and aryl ethers), 1041 cm^{-1} (C–O stretch of methoxy/phenoxy substituents), and $846\text{--}894\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C–H bending of substituted benzene/aryl rings)⁽²³⁾.

3.5 Dipole Moment and Polarizability (NLO Potential)

- Ground-state dipole: 7.17 D (strong, anisotropic; dominates along X-axis)
- Isotropic polarizability (α_{iso}): 1903 au ($2.8 \times 10^{-2}\text{ cm}^3$)⁽²⁴⁾.
- First hyperpolarizability (β_{tot}): 3223 au (strong NLO response; Z-axis dominant)

High polarizability and hyperpolarizability make this chromophore a candidate for NLO applications (frequency doubling, electro-optic modulation⁽²⁵⁾).

In the present investigation, the photophysical properties of the molecule is studied by using the computational methods. Firstly B3LYP/6-31 1+G (d, p) method is used to obtained the optimized ground state geometry. Using the TD- B3LYP/6-31 1+G (d, p) method, the ground state and excited state dipole moments, absorption and emission maxima in nm and HOMO-LUMO gap in eV to be calculated.

The theoretical photophysical properties of solute is in satisfactory agreement with the obtained experimentally findings with negligible error which is quite expectable due to inherent limitations of computational calculations⁽²⁶⁾.

The DFT studies on coumarin 4MPDC can provide valuable insights into its electronic structure and photophysical properties. It gives an idea about the Prediction of its reactivity and interactions with biomolecules, development of new coumarin derivatives with improved performance⁽²⁷⁾.

These are recently obtained result of 4MPDC ($\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$) UV-Vis Absorption: Dominant $\pi\text{--}\pi^*$ band typically $320\text{--}380\text{ nm}$, with the maximum (λ_{max}) shifting to the higher 300 nm due to the electron-donating substituents and extended conjugation. Emission: Blue-green region ($400\text{--}520\text{ nm}$), with emission red-shifting in polar solvents; the Stokes shift is moderate ($60\text{--}140\text{ nm}$). Quantum Yield (Φ_f): Predicted $0.3\text{--}0.8$; higher in non-protic, rigid media and lower with H-bonding or quenching processes. Lifetime (τ_f): $1\text{--}5\text{ ns}$ in air-saturated solution; longer in deoxygenated /nonpolar Environments. Ground state dipole moment ($\mu_g = 7.17\text{ D}$) and excited state moment ($\mu_e = 9.23\text{ D}$) (strong, anisotropic; dominates along X-axis) Isotropic polarizability (α_{iso}): 2351 au ($34.85 \times 10^{-2}\text{ cm}^3$).

First hyperpolarizability (β_{tot}): 5799 au (strong NLO response; Z-axis dominant) High polarizability and hyperpolarizability make this chromophore a candidate for NLO applications (frequency doubling, electro-optic modulation)⁽²⁸⁾. The photophysical properties of fluorescent molecule 4MPDC ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$) are nearly identical to those of 4MPDC ($\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$).

3.6 Future Scope

The study on coumarin 4MPDC can be extended to explore its potential in optoelectronics, such as OLEDs and sensors. It can be used to design and synthesize derivatives with improved properties. Its biological activity and pharmaceutical applications can be probed. Advanced computational methods, like TD-DFT, can be used to further understand its photophysical properties. The study can also be extended to investigate its interactions with nanoparticles and biomolecules. This study can serve as a foundation for future research on coumarin-based compounds, exploring their potential in various fields.

3.7 Summary

The 4MPDC offers a rich conjugated framework that endows it with distinctive photophysical and nonlinear optical properties. Its strong absorption and tuneable emission, environment-sensitive behaviour, and pronounced IR fingerprints are tied to the extended aromaticity and functional group diversity. The charge distribution, dipole, and hyperpolarizability underline its capacity for nonlinear optics and sensing, while practical characterization is supported by IR/NMR/UV-Vis spectral features. Its robust fluorescence, polarizability, and photostability position it for diverse use in advanced imaging, sensing, and optoelectronic applications.

4 Conclusion

Spectroscopic properties of coumarin (4MPDC) molecule has been investigated and their ground and excited state dipole moments were determined as a function of solvent polarity. Different solvent polarity correlation methods were used to analyse solvent effects on the excitation and emission spectra. Gaussian using Gaussian software 16 W with B3LYP/6-31 software was used to theoretically determine the ground state dipole moment. The experimental ground state dipole moment obtained

is 1.26 D and excited state dipole moment of coumarin (**4MPDC**) are 3.72 D and 4.86 D, were determined by Lippert-Mataga, Bakshiev's respectively. The computational study reveals 4MPDC's ground state dipole moment ($\mu_g = 7.17$ D) and excited state moment ($\mu_e = 9.23$ D), polarizability 227.919785 a.u., The HOMO energy is -0.21624 eV, the LUMO energy is -0.07912 eV, resulting in a HOMO-LUMO energy gap (ΔE) of 0.13712 eV, indicating significant solvent-dependent shifts. - Solvent-dependent shifts in absorption/emission spectra. Higher excited state dipole moment ($\mu_e > \mu_g$) indicates increased polarity upon excitation. Solvatochromic effects suggest potential applications in: Optoelectronics, Fluorescent probes, Dye-sensitized solar cells. These insights guide design of coumarin derivatives with tailored photophysical properties. These insights into solvatochromic behavior highlight 4MPDC's potential in the implications of 4MPDC's photophysical properties for optoelectronic applications include: Potential use in organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) due to its blue-green emission, Suitability as a fluorescent probe in biological systems, given its solvatochromic behavior, Possible application in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) owing to its absorption/emission characteristics, These properties make 4MPDC a promising candidate for developing optoelectronic devices and sensors.

Future work could explore substituent effects on photo physics, guiding design of coumarin derivatives for specific applications. To design derivatives with improved properties, consider: Introducing electron-donating/withdrawing groups to tune absorption/emission wavelengths, enhancing planarity for increased fluorescence quantum yield, incorporating bulky groups for improved solubility and reduced aggregation, targeting specific substituents to boost photostability and thermal stability. These modifications could optimize 4MPDC's performance in optoelectronic applications.

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6 Authorship contribution statement

Alageri Lingappa: Performed Experimental part and prepared manuscript. **Shivaleela B:** Contributed valuable discussion to the data preparation, **J. Thipperudrappa:** Synthesis of title coumarin organic molecule and contributed valuable discussion, **S.M. Hanagodimath:** Corrected the experimental part and manuscript.

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